

REVIEW ARTICLE

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Efficiency of Clear Aligners for Intrusion of Teeth: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Background: Clear aligners have gained popularity due to their aesthetics and ease of use compared with fixed appliances. Although initially indicated for mild to moderate malocclusions, they are now increasingly used in complex cases as well. However, their biomechanics and predictability of anterior intrusion remain uncertain, with variable reported efficiency. Therefore, this systematic review evaluates the effectiveness of clear aligners for anterior teeth intrusion and highlights future research on their role in deep bite management. **Objectives:** The aim of this systematic review was to investigate the intrusion efficiency of clear aligners in correction of deep bite cases. **Method:** Electronic search of Google Scholar, Scopus, PubMed and Cochrane CENTRAL, along with hand searching of selected orthodontic journals (2005–2025) was performed. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined using the PICOS framework. Of 39 identified records, 22 full texts were assessed, and 5 studies met the inclusion criteria. Intrusion efficiency of was evaluated by comparing predicted and achieved intrusion using Clin Check software, CBCT, digital model superimposition and lateral cephalograms. **Findings:** Results of all studies showed that the predicted intrusion value was more as compared to the actual value with a mean intrusion efficiency ranging between 51% to 73%. Biomechanical control improved with the use of auxiliaries, enhancing anterior intrusive forces. Age influenced outcomes, with greater intrusion observed in adolescents (63.5%) than adults (45.3%), highlighting the need for overcorrection and hybrid mechanics in adults. Despite lower clinical efficiency compared to predictions, clear aligners were effective in deep bite correction at both skeletal and dentoalveolar levels and remain a viable alternative to fixed appliances when appropriate overcorrection is incorporated into aligner software to get required intrusion. **Novelty/Significance:** This review offers clinically applicable guidance for planning deep bite treatment with clear aligners while emphasizing the need for further research on aligner-mediated tooth movement.

Keywords: Clear Aligners; Deep bite; Intrusion of teeth; Aesthetics

1 Introduction

In recent decades, growing social awareness and the influence of social media has made individuals conscious of their smile and facial aesthetics. A pleasing smile is often associated with confidence, attractiveness, and social acceptance, leading more patients, especially adolescents and adults to seek orthodontic care. However, concerns regarding visibility of traditional braces, discomfort, and treatment duration has encouraged the development of more aesthetic and patient-friendly alternatives⁽¹⁾. Due to these increasing patients demands, it has led to the emergence of options such as clear aligners, ceramic brackets, lingual orthodontics, and minimally invasive adjunctive procedures, allowing clinicians to provide effective treatment while meeting patients expectations for comfort, discretion, and improved appearance during therapy. Development of clear aligners has served this purpose as being an aesthetic alternative to fixed appliances.

Aligners are used to treat various malocclusions like deep bite, open bite, expansion, spacing and extraction cases as well and currently are being the popular choice amongst adolescents and adults. Despite their growing popularity, their biomechanical principles underlying different tooth movements remains incompletely understood⁽²⁾. Correction of deep-bite malocclusions with aligners is biomechanically challenging for orthodontists. Specifically, research has shown that orthodontists struggle to achieve mandibular incisor intrusion with clear aligners which remains one of it's least accurate movements^{(3), (4), (5)}.

Specifically, Invisalign aligners struggles to achieve mandibular incisor intrusion^{(6), (7)}. Tooth movement studies conducted over the past 15 years have shown that the accuracy of mandibular incisor intrusion with Invisalign ranges from 25–45%. The results are often prolonged treatment with minimal over bite improvement.

There are several factors contributing to the lower accuracy of mandibular incisor intrusion with Invisalign. The most notable factors are patient noncompliance, loss of anchorage (aligner liftoff in the posterior region), posterior intrusion (patient's natural biting force) and improper virtual case setup in Clin Check.

Despite various advantages of clear aligners over fixed appliances, their biomechanical disadvantages frequently off set them. Therefore, to improve biomechanical control, Align Technology introduced Smart Force features in 2008, SmartTrack aligner material in 2011. In 2014, they introduced Invisalign G5 Innovation for Deep Bite correction. This innovation included control of anterior intrusion via Smart Force pressure areas (to direct intrusion through the long axis of the tooth), optimized deep bite attachments on premolars (to serve as anchorage for incisor intrusion), and precision bite ramps that are up to 3 mm in depth (to allow posterior disocclusion). These bite ramps were designed to eliminate transient posterior intrusion and add intrusive forces to mandibular incisors through natural biting forces.

An integral aspect of Invisalign therapy is its virtual treatment-planning software Clin Check, which demonstrates the specific tooth movements required to idealize each patient's occlusion and allows the clinician to sequence these movements to maximize efficiency. Although the software builds in 0.25mm of intrusion per tray, experienced Invisalign providers are aware that virtual Clin Check treatment does not always accurately represent clinical results. To compensate, they usually add a significant amount of overcorrection to their virtual treatment plans.

Studies conducted by Nguyen and Cheng measured actual anterior intrusion obtained with Invisalign as a percentage of amount requested in Clin Check. They reported a mean accuracy of 79%⁽⁸⁾. In contrast, Kravitz and colleagues found a mean accuracy of only 46.6%. Rossini and colleagues, in a systematic review determined that clear aligners could be used to treat simple malocclusions with "light overbite discrepancies"⁽⁹⁾. However, Hong et al. found that adding attachments could aid in achieving orthodontic intrusion movements with clear aligners⁽¹⁰⁾.

However, numerous methods including the American Board of Orthodontics objective grading system, peer assessment rating systems, and other objective occlusal criteria, have been used by scholars to evaluate the quality of orthodontic treatment with clear aligners⁽¹¹⁾. The conclusions were that clear aligners are not an effective appliance for managing overbites⁽¹²⁾.

Due to such conflicting results of various studies and lack of knowledge of biomechanical principles of clear aligners in achieving anterior teeth intrusion, it has encouraged us to undertake this systematic review.

2 Review Methodology

The PRISMA checklist was used as a guideline for conducting this systematic review and the protocol for the same was registered in the PROSPERO database (CRD420251047301).

2.1 Information sources, search strategy and study selection:

Electronic and hand searches were used to identify all studies, regardless of language. An electronic search was conducted using Google Scholar, Scopus, PubMed and Cochrane CENTRAL with the year of coverage from 2005 to 2025. The search strategy is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Search methodology for electronic systematic review

Search engine	Search terms
1. Google scholar, PubMed, CENTRAL	'Clear aligners', 'Clear aligners AND intrusion', 'Clear aligners OR intrusion', 'Clear aligners AND incisor intrusion', 'Clear aligners AND deep bite', 'Clear aligners AND TADs', 'Clear aligners AND temporary skeletal anchorage devices'
2. Scopus	'Clear aligner therapy' OR 'Clear aligners', 'Clear aligners AND intrusion' OR 'Clear aligners AND incisor intrusion' OR 'Clear aligners OR incisor intrusion' OR 'Clear aligners AND deep bite'

A hand search also was undertaken to identify relevant studies from the following journals: American Journal of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopedics, Angle Orthodontist, Seminars in Orthodontics, and Journal of Clinical Orthodontics.

The authors of the included studies were contacted by the review authors to obtain further information about additional or unpublished studies that were eligible for inclusion in the review.

2.2 Eligibility criteria

The eligibility criteria for the selection of studies includes inclusion and exclusion criteria. It is established using the PICOS (Population Intervention Comparator Outcome and Study design) format as depicted in Table 2.

Table 2. PICOS framework

Sr. no	PICOS component	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
1.	Population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients undergoing orthodontic treatment with clear aligners. Patients aged between 15-45 years. Patients with Angle's Class I, Class II or Class III malocclusion with deep bite 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients undergoing orthodontic treatment with fixed appliance. Patients aged <12 years. Patients with skeletal Class II or Class III malocclusion. Scissorbite and crossbite cases. Surgical cases. Cleft cases and periodontally compromised cases.
2.	Intervention	clear aligners with or without the use of auxiliaries like bite ramps, elastics, attachments and TADs.	Fixed appliances
3.	Comparison	No comparator for this study	
4.	Outcome	Clinical accuracy of intrusion efficiency of clear aligners	
5.	Study design	Non randomised controlled trials including retrospective and prospective studies	Randomised controlled trials, case reports, systematic reviews and meta-analysis

2.3 Outcomes

The primary outcome was the percentage of intrusion achieved with clear aligners (Invisalign) as measured by comparing predicted and actual intrusion achieved through various methods including (Clin check) software, cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) scans, superimposition of digital models and lateral cephalograms.

2.4 Study selection

Two review authors identified potentially relevant studies independently by screening the titles and abstracts resulting from the searches. The full text of each potentially relevant study was obtained, and inclusion was assessed independently and in duplicate. In case of disagreement regarding the inclusion or exclusion of a study, it was resolved by a third reviewer. The study selection process is depicted in the following PRISMA flowchart.

2.5 Data extraction

After selection of the studies, the full data extraction was independently performed by 2 reviewers using a pre-designed table. The data extracted from each study were (1) Author, journal name, and year of publication; (2) Type of study (3) Auxiliary elements used (4) Average age of the patients (5) Number of patients (6) Outcome measures (7) Results. Characteristics of the included studies are represented in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of the included studies

Author, year and journal	Type of study	Auxiliary elements used	No. of patients	Mean age of patients	Outcome measures	Results
1. Al-Balaa <i>et al</i> , AJODO, 2021	Retrospective	No auxiliaries used	22	23.74 yrs	CBCT scans and Clin check software	precision of upper and lower anterior teeth intrusion achieved 51.19% with highest intrusion accuracy (58.12%) for maxillary lateral incisors and lowest accuracy (44.71%) for mandibular incisors.
2. Yan <i>et al</i> , Progress in orthodontics, 2023	Retrospective	Elastics and labial mini-implants	51	25.1 yrs	Superimposition of digital models and Clin check software	precision of upper incisor intrusion achieved 53.3%
3. Henick <i>et al</i> , Angle Orthodontist, 2021	Retrospective	Bite ramps and Class II elastics used	48	>18 yrs	Lateral cephalograms	Upper and lower incisor intrusion, overbite reduction, lower anterior face height increase and increase in mandibular plane angle was less in clear aligners as compared to fixed appliance but still clear aligners were effective in opening deep bite both at skeletal and dentoalveolar levels.
4. Glassick <i>et al</i> , JCO, 2017	Retrospective	No auxiliaries used	30	29.4 yrs	Lateral cephalograms and Clin check software	73% lower incisor intrusion accuracy observed.
5. Kravitz <i>et al</i> , Angle orthodontist, 2024	Prospective	Bite ramps and attachments used	58	Adolscents- 15.1 yrs Adults- 40.7 yrs	Superimposition of digital models	More accurate lower incisor intrusion was seen in adolescents (63.5%) than adults (45.3%)

*no specific time duration for aligner wear was specified in the above studies

2.6 Risk of bias of the selected studies

Two authors assessed the risk of bias for all the included studies with a third reviewer resolving any disagreements.

From the total included studies, about 4 were retrospective studies and only 1 was prospective study. For prospective studies and retrospective studies, the risk of bias assessment was done using New Castle Ottawa scale.

The scale varied considerably across the studies, ranging from a score of 6/9 to 8/9, the main issues being selection and definition of controls as it wasn't applicable to majority of the studies. Secondly, lack of adjustment for potential confounders in case of prospective study included also reported a risk of bias (Table 4).

Table 4. Study Quality as Assessed by the Newcastle Ottawa Scale as Judged by the 2 Reviewers Who Performed Data Extraction

References	Selection (Maximum, 4 Asterisks)	Comparability (Maximum, 2 Asterisks)	Exposure/Intervention (Maximum, 3 Asterisks)
(13)	**	**	**
(14)	**	**	**
(15)	**	**	**
(16)	**	**	**
(17)	****	*	***

2.7 Certainty assessment

The quality of the available evidence was assessed using the GRADEpro GDT tool.

2.8 Statistical analysis

Meta-analysis was not performed due to the heterogeneity of the techniques, and outcomes measured in each study. Since there were only 5 separate studies included in this systematic review, each study will be assessed and discussed separately.

3 Overview

Clear aligners have gained increasing popularity among adolescents and adults due to their aesthetic appeal and improved comfort compared with conventional fixed appliances. Initially, clear aligner therapy was recommended primarily for orthodontic patients presenting with mild to moderate malocclusions.⁽¹⁸⁾ However, recent literature has reported successful management of more complex orthodontic cases using clear aligners. Despite these advancements, there is still lack of knowledge regarding biomechanical control of aligners in achieving various types of tooth movements. Specifically, studies evaluating the efficiency of anterior teeth intrusion with clear aligners remain limited and have shown variable efficacy resulting in conflicting results. Therefore, studies with enormous sample sizes and rigorous research designs are required to comprehend how clear aligners correct malocclusion. The best evidence in assessing intrusion efficiency achieved by clear aligners consists of 5 studies in this systematic review. Each study is discussed in detail as follows-

Al-Balaa *et al*, in the first retrospective study compared the predicted (Clin Check software) and actual anterior teeth intrusion using CBCT. The sample size was 22 patients including 142 teeth (12 females and 10 males) with a mean age of 23.74 years (ranging from 16 years to 46 years 8 months) who underwent orthodontic treatment with Invisalign clear aligners only. The overbite status was normal in 8 patients (ranging from 1.80 to 4.00 mm) and 14 patients had a deep overbite with a mean of 4.18 mm. The average treatment period was 19.27 months (ranging from 11 months to 29 months). The patients had to wear each aligner for 14 days. Each patient in this study started treatment after Align Technology introduced the Smart Track material and launched their deep bite protocol. Patients had pressure areas on the lingual cingulum and were treated without bite ramps, potentially enhancing aligner performance. A mean intrusion efficacy of 51.19% was found across all anterior teeth. Maxillary lateral incisors had the highest accuracy (58.12%), while mandibular incisors had the lowest (44.71%). Other teeth showed moderate accuracy: maxillary central incisors (51.83%), maxillary canines (48.95%), and mandibular canines (52.34%). The mean amount of true intrusion achieved was 0.90 mm. All patients required refinement aligners, indicating initial plans were insufficient to fully meet treatment goals. Retrospective design posed a risk of selection bias, though patient compliance was monitored similarly to other studies⁽¹⁹⁾.

Yan *et al*, in his retrospective study compared the predicted (Clin Check software) and actual anterior teeth intrusion (intra-oral scans) by superimposing these digital dental models. The sample size was 51 patients having Class II division 2 malocclusion including 173 upper anterior teeth (38 females and 13 males) with a mean age of 25.1 years who underwent orthodontic treatment with Invisalign clear aligners only. All the participants were asked to wear clear aligners for at least 22 hours per day and to change aligners every 10 days. Specifically, labial mini-implants were placed between upper central incisors or between central and lateral incisors and orthodontic elastics were worn from the palatal precision cuts of clear aligners to the labial mini-implants. The results of the study showed that actual incisor intrusion was (0.8mm) 53.3% which was less than the predicted value (1.5mm). The DPA (difference between predicted and actual incisor intrusion) is increased with more predicted intrusion amount or without labial mini-implants, thus needing overtreatment of intrusion. The limitation of this study was smaller sample size but nonetheless this study provided preliminary evidence for further randomised controlled trials to testify incisor tooth movements with clear aligners⁽²⁰⁾.

Henick *et al* in his retrospective study investigated the skeletal and dentoalveolar effects of Invisalign's G5 protocol with virtual bite ramps in the treatment of adults with skeletal deep bites. Forty-eight subjects were divided into 2 groups: Invisalign group treated with the Invisalign G5 protocol and a full fixed appliance (FFA) group treated with edgewise FFAs consisting of 24 subjects each group. Both the groups were matched depending upon Overbite Depth Indicator (ODI), sex, type of malocclusion and non-extraction treatment. Pretreatment (T1) and post comprehensive treatment (T2) lateral cephalograms were obtained and analysed. A total of 9 skeletal, 8 dental and 3 soft tissue variables were measured. Of the measurements, 10 were linear and 10 were angular. FFA group was treated with 0.018-inch slot MBT prescription brackets. The results showed that both the Invisalign and FFA groups showed significant changes from T1 to T2 in ODI and other skeletal and dentoalveolar measurements. The mean change in ODI was -1.5° for the Invisalign group and -2.0° for the FFA group. The mean decrease in overbite was 1.3 mm and 2.0 mm for the Invisalign and FFA groups respectively and the mean increase in mandibular plane angle (Sn-GoGn) was 0.65° for

the Invisalign group and 1.15⁰ for the FFA group. The ANS–Menton distance increased significantly in both groups, more so in the FFA group (1.85 mm vs. 0.64 mm in Invisalign), indicating increased facial height. Maxillary incisor intrusion was 1.14 mm in the FFA group and 0.88 mm in the Invisalign group. Only 37.5% of Invisalign patients had torque prescribed. Mandibular incisor intrusion was significantly greater in the FFA group (2.06 mm vs. 1.30 mm with Invisalign), though Invisalign achieved this with minimal flaring. Invisalign's G5 pressure areas effectively enabled true intrusion without significant proclination of the mandibular incisors. Molars extruded significantly in both groups. Although, patient compliance was not measured but could have influenced Invisalign results. Therefore, even though clear aligners showed less intrusion efficiency as compared to fixed appliances, they were effective in opening deep bite both at skeletal as well as dentoalveolar level.⁽¹⁴⁾

Glassick *et al* evaluated the efficacy of lower incisor intrusion using the Invisalign system compared to the amount of virtual tooth movement requested in Clin Check. They obtained pre (T1) and post-intrusion (T2) lateral cephalometric records from 30 consecutive non-growing adult patients comprising of 11 males and 19 females, with a mean starting age of 29.4 years (range of 18–63). All cases involved SmartTrack material and two-week aligner change intervals. No bite ramps were used in any of the patients. True absolute intrusion was measured using the centre of resistance (CR), though its definition and measurement may introduce variability. The authors concluded that the mean amount of incisor intrusion requested in Clin Check was 2.19mm, but the mean amount of intrusion obtained clinically was 1.49mm, resulting in a mean difference of 0.71mm and a mean intrusion accuracy of 73%. This accuracy was higher than Kravitz *et al.* (46.6%) and close to Nguyen and Cheng's 79%. This improvement may be due to newer SmartTrack aligner material and the use of lateral cephalograms instead of virtual models. Clinicians in the study typically planned for overcorrection in Clin Check, helping achieve desired outcomes despite under-intrusion and they devised a formula for the same though, it requires further validation. However, the drawbacks of this study were small sample size, lack of randomization and retrospective study design⁽¹⁶⁾.

Kravitz *et al* in his prospective study, compared the accuracy of mandibular incisor intrusion with Invisalign in adolescents to that in adults. The sample group comprised 58 patients who were divided into two groups of 29 adults and 29 adolescents. There were 16 male and 42 female patients. The mean ages were 15.1years in the adolescent group and 40.7years in the adult group. The total number of mandibular incisors measured was 232, including 116 central and 116 lateral incisors and the mean number of aligners in the lower arch was 22.4. Adolescent patients received Invisalign Teen, while adult patients received Invisalign Full. Except for the compliance tabs feature, there was no difference between Invisalign Teen and Invisalign Full, as they utilized the same aligner material and tooth movement sequencing. Auxiliaries such as bite ramps on the maxillary incisors, G5 attachments on the mandibular premolars and first molars and 4.0 mm horizontal bevelled attachments on the mandibular lateral incisors and canines were used. Predicted values were determined by superimposing the initial and final Clin Check models and achieved values were determined by superimposing the initial Clin Check models and the digital models from the final intraoral scans. Individual teeth were superimposed with a best-fit analysis and measured using Compare software (version 8.1; Geo Digm, Falcon Heights, Minn). The result of the study was that the accuracy of mandibular incisor intrusion was 63.5% in adolescents and 45.3% in adults also, the amounts of achieved intrusion was 1.7 mm in adolescents and 0.9 mm in adults, and both these differences were statistically significant. A negative correlation between age and intrusion accuracy was observed. This could be attributed to vertical ramal growth, molar eruption and bone remodelling in adolescents or increased occlusal forces or enamel wear in adults. Reverse curve of Spee mechanics and horizontal attachments enhanced intrusion accuracy. The authors therefore concluded that the amount of achieved intrusion was significantly larger in adolescents than in adults and as patient age advances, the accuracy of mandibular incisor intrusion diminishes slightly. Less overcorrection may be needed in adolescents, while adults may require hybrid mechanics. However, Clin Check limitations and single-provider involvement were notable study constraints⁽¹⁵⁾.

Thus, the results of all the studies showed that the predicted value of tooth intrusion was more as compared to the actual value with a mean intrusion efficiency ranging between 51% to 73%. The biomechanical control of clear aligners was improved with the use of auxiliaries which helped in increasing the intrusive forces on anterior teeth. Apart from this, it was observed that age also had an influence on anterior teeth intrusion, which was found to be more in adolescents (63.5%) as compared to adults (45.3%) indicating the need of overcorrection and use of hybrid mechanics in adult patients. Therefore, although the intrusion efficiency of clear aligners was less clinically as compared to its predicted value, still they proved to be successful in opening deep bite both at skeletal and dentoalveolar level. Thus, they serve as a good alternative to fixed appliances in treatment of deep bite cases with the need of overcorrection in the aligner software to get the required intrusion.

Future studies should evaluate Class II elastic wear, crowding effects and 3D model analysis for better insight. Therefore, intrusion planning in aligner software is critical and overengineering intrusion and extrusion movements is a key to success in treating deep bite cases using clear aligners.

4 Conclusion

Clear aligners have expanded orthodontic treatment options for adolescents and adults and is useful in managing various malocclusions. Despite growing evidence, gaps remain in the literature in understanding their biomechanical control. Also, studies till date have shown variable intrusion efficacy with clear aligners leading to conflicting results. Therefore, this systematic review focused on determining the intrusion efficiency of clear aligners and reported that actual intrusion achieved was lower than predicted, with mean efficiency ranging from 51%–73%. The use of auxiliaries improved intrusive force delivery and age influenced outcomes, with greater intrusion seen in adolescents than adults, indicating the need for overcorrection and hybrid mechanics in adult patients. Nevertheless, clear aligners were effective in correcting deep bite at both skeletal and dentoalveolar levels and can serve as a reliable alternative to fixed appliances when appropriate treatment planning and overcorrection is incorporated in aligner software along with the use of auxiliaries.

Limitations of the study:

1. This study doesn't specify any particular time duration for the aligner wear to see the intrusion efficiency of aligners.
2. This study takes into consideration only one aligner brand i.e. Invisalign, however due to emerging new aligner companies and development of in house aligners, more number of studies on other aligner brands should also be carried out.
3. Also, the retention protocol of the aligners was not specified to see the long term results.
4. More number of randomised controlled trials with larger sample size are required.

Future scope:

As with the emerging trend of aligners, future studies can be performed to check the efficiency of different clear aligner materials on various types of tooth movement and also to study the aligner effects on tooth movement at a biological level.

5 Contributory statement

Conceptualization of study problem: Dr. Srushtee Jagtap, Experimental Design: Dr. Srushtee Jagtap & Dr. Vinit Swami, Data analysis: Dr. Srushtee Jagtap, Dr. Shrushti Bapat & Dr. Ankita Pawar, Research Guidance: Dr. Vinit Swami and Dr. Veera Bhosale, Original Drafting or Writing: Dr. Srushtee Jagtap, Editing & Reviewing: Dr. Vinit Swami & Dr. Vasanthi Swami.

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